

RURAL CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING IN POLLACHI TALUK

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Abstract:

Online shopping is a recent phenomenon in electronic commerce and its definitely going to be the future of shopping in the world. It is user friendly compare to in store shopping because consumers can just complete his requirements just with a click of mouse without leaving their home. In the present work, the researcher intended to analyze the most preferred online shopping website, factors influencing the rural customers towards online shopping and to analyze the level satisfaction of the rural online customers in Pollachi Taluk. To analyze the online shopping satisfaction of rural customers, the required data has been collected from 150 respondents. Simple average method, Factor analysis and chi square analysis were used.

Key Words: Online Shopping, Factors Influencing, Rural Consumer Behavior, Consumer & Consumer Satisfaction

Introduction:

Online shopping is a recent phenomenon in electronic commerce and its definitely going to be the future of shopping in the world. Almost all the business units are selling their products/services in online. Youth's inquisitiveness towards online shopping is ever increasing. The youth's perception towards online shopping is totally different; they see this as new fashion, time saving, easy accessible, variety and with more interesting. In the beginning stage people thought about online shopping was low security, poor in quality and untrustworthy. But gradually, the perception has changed and at the moment it is showing positive signs among youth's. Due to ever-increasing internet and mobile penetration, growing acceptability of electronic payments has provided the unique opportunity to companies to connect with their customers. Today both urban and rural areas are enjoying internet facilities. The increasing use of internet by the young generation in India provides an emerging prospect for online traders. Unlike traditional marketing, online marketing has many advantages like global reach, availability of wide variety, cheaper products and 24X7 timing etc. It creates a craze among young generation because previously where they spent a lot of time for shopping, but now-a-days just by sitting at home they can browse through many websites and choose the best deal and place an order within few minutes.

Review of Literature:

Anders Hasslinger, Selma Hodzic and Claudio Opazo (2007) examined particular factors that influence the online consumer with reference to university of kristianstad student. In this research, price, trust, and convenience were identified as important factors. Price was considered to be the most important factor for majority of the students.

Sharma and Mittal (2009) in their study "Prospects of ecommerce in India", mention that India is showing tremendous growth in e-commerce. Undoubtedly, with the population of millions of people, online shopping shows unlimited potential in India. Today e-commerce is a common word in Indian society and it has become an integral part of our daily life. There are websites providing a number of goods and services. Then there are those, which provide a specific product along with its allied services- multi-product e-commerce. These Indian e-commerce portals provide goods and services in a variety of categories.

Banerjee, Dutta, and Dasgupta (2010) conducted a study on "customer's attitude towards online shopping". The study revealed that among the 202 respondents who shopped online, 89.1% were satisfied and 96.1% satisfied customers also intended to indulge in online shopping in the future. It could be concluded that the availability of extensive and current information was the most important factor which influenced Indian customers to shop online. The researcher also revealed that there was a significant association between online shopping and monthly family income, frequency of internet usage, and time spent per session on Internet usage.

Kanwalgurleen (2012) discussed that different options in internet encouraged them to search and eventually purchase online, because more than 100 million internet users in India. People those who are using internet from 5 to 7 hours a day were found to be adopter of online shopping. Price consciousness, convenience and variety, easy payment options and challenges of online shopping are the factors found to be a significant in online shopping. Without rush traffic and vehicles one can purchase a huge variety of product by spending minimum timing.

Adrita Goswami et.al (2013) Studied "Customer Satisfaction towards Online Shopping with Special Reference to Teenage Group of Jorhat Town" study concludes that online customers are satisfied. This research

explicitly indicates that online marketer should give more importance on price factor and after sale factor. In this competition era all the online marketers should have to concentrate on the customer's satisfaction to retain the existing customers and have to offer new scheme day by day to attract the new customers.

Ashish Pant (2014) concluded in his research article that a successful web store is not the just a good looking website with the dynamic technical features but is also emphasis on building the relationship with customers with making money. Firstly understanding the customer's needs and wants is very essential for building a relation with the customers keeping companies' promises gives a customer a reason to come back and meeting the expectations gives them a reason to stay.

Mohanapriya. S and Anusuya. D, (2014) all types of commodities and services are being sold through the websites. Goods and services, consumer durables, books, audio and video cassettes and services like and air tickets can also be purchased online. With the wonderful expansion of the internet, online shopping is also on the rise, showing fabulous potential for future growth, as well.

Shadi Altarifi et al. (2015) in their paper found that the determinants of marketing have insignificant influence the consumer purchasing decision, while cultural and technological determinants had significant influence on consumer buying decision. The researchers recommend protection strategies in the adoption of preventive e-business networks, which are made through the Internet and an intensive awareness programs aimed to show the advantages shopping services via the Internet.

Statement of the Problem:

Marketing is basically helps to fulfill the needs of the consumer's more effectively and efficiently with good product/services with affordable price and delivery. A good marketer continuously satisfying consumers needs in better way. Sometimes opportunity to give the consumers in better way is designed by marketers himself and sometimes it is offered by the technology. In recent days the concept of online shopping has gained a lot of importance in retail marketing. In India almost 75% of online users are in the age group of 15 – 34 years since India is one of the youngest demography globally. This trend is expected to be continuing in forthcoming years, given the age distribution in India. Along with the rapid growth of online shopping fraudulent practices and cheating also increased. Such cheating activities had created fear in the minds of customers and also an adverse impact in the attitude of consumers towards online shopping. As the majority of the people living in villages, rural market capacity is larger than urban. Based on the above statement the researcher has raised the following research question;

- ✓ What is the most preferred online shopping website?
- ✓ What are the factors influencing customers towards online shopping?
- ✓ What are factors that have the maximum impact on customer satisfaction of online shopping?

Study Objective:

- ✓ To ascertain the most preferred online shopping websites among the customers.
- ✓ To analyze the factors influencing customers towards online shopping.
- ✓ To analyze the satisfaction level of customers towards online shopping.
- ✓ To investigate the major factors that have the maximum impact on customer satisfaction of online shopping

Sampling Plan and Tool:

The study is based on primary data. The researcher collected required data from the respondents who have actively involved in online shopping. For the collection of primary data, 150 respondents were selected through convenient sampling method. The data were collected by using well structured questionnaire. To analyze the socio economic factors simple percentage method adopted, Chi-square test and Factor analysis used to find out most influencing factors towards online shopping.

Area and Period of Study:

The present study is based on Consumers perceptions, so the sample consumers have been selected from different parts of Pollachi taluk. The period of study ranges from January 2016 to July 2016.

Scope of the Study:

The present study is undertaken to analyze the level of satisfaction of the rural customers towards online shopping. It enables us to understand the key factors that have the highest impact on customer satisfaction of online shopping. In short, the study covers only socio economic status, most preferred online shopping website, factors influencing customers towards online shopping and factors satisfying customers.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Demographic consideration of the respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	95	63.3
Female	55	36.7
Total	150	100.0
Age	Frequency	Percentage
Below 20	28	18.7

21-30	66	44.0
31-40	51	34.0
Above 41	5	3.3
Total	150	100.0
Marital status	Frequency	Percentage
Married	67	44.7
Unmarried	83	55.3
Total	150	100.0
Educational qualification	Frequency	Percentage
Up to high school	26	17.3
Undergraduate	99	66.0
Postgraduate and professional	25	16.7
Total	150	100.0
Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Students	43	28.7
Employee	67	44.7
Business	13	8.7
Agriculturist	12	8.0
Professionals	9	6.0
Others specify	6	4.0
Total	150	100.0
Monthly income	Frequency	Percentage
Up to Rs.15,000	32	21.3
Rs.15,001-25,000	74	49.3
Rs25,001-35,000	39	26.0
Above Rs 35,000	5	3.3
Total	150	100.0

Source: Primary data

The gender distribution of the respondents consisting (63.3%) of male respondents and (36.7%) of female respondents. The major age group of online buyers was below 20 years. (18.7%) followed by 21 to 30 years (44%), 31 to 40 years (34%) and above 40 years (3.3%). The marital status of the respondents was, with (44.7%) married respondents and (55.3%) unmarried respondents. In terms of education qualification, majority (66%) of the respondents were undergraduates, (17.3%) of the respondents were up to high school, and (16.7%) of the respondents were postgraduate and professional. in terms of occupation, almost (44.7%) of the respondents were employees,(28.7%) of the respondents were students,(8.7%) of the respondents were engaged them in business(81%) of the respondents were agriculturist, (6%) of the respondents were professionals.(4%) of the respondents they are house wife's. with regards to monthly income of online buyers, the major group of online shoppers had monthly income of Rs.15,001- Rs.25,000(26%) , followed by Rs. 25,001- 35,000, (21%) followed by up to Rs. 15,000, and (5%) of the respondents are monthly earning income were above Rs. 35,000 p.m.

Table 2: Online Buying Behaviour of the respondents

Online Buying Behaviour	Classification	Frequency	Percentage
Frequency of purchase	Once per month	90	60.0
	Once in 3 months	26	17.3
	Once in 6 months	31	20.7
	Once in a year	3	2.0
Factors influencing on line purchases	No hidden cost	22	14.7
	Variety of products	44	29.3
	Quality	81	54
	Others	3	2
Category of products	Electronic goods/ equipment	55	36.7
	Clothing /Life styles	14	9.3
	Books	9	6.0
	Home appliances	38	25.3
	Tours / hotel reservation / Online ticket reservation	31	20.7
	Others (specify)	3	2.0

Most preferred web site	Myntra.com	12	8
	Amazon	64	42.7
	Flipkart	47	31.3
	E-bay	9	6
	Snapdeal	15	10
	Others	3	2

Source: Primary data

The above table shows that 60% of the respondents are buys Once in a month, 20 % of the respondents are buys six month once, 17.3% of the respondents are buys three month once, and 2% of the respondents are buys once in a year. 54% of the respondents are looks Quality as a factor for purchasing product on online, 29.3 % of the respondents are having Varity of products, 14.7% of the respondents are feels no hidden cost and 2% of the respondents are said others factors. 36.7% of the respondents purchased Electronic goods/ equipment, 25.3% of the respondents are purchased Home appliances, 20.7% of the respondents purchased Tours / hotel reservation / online ticket reservation, 9.3% of the respondents purchased clothing /Life styles, 6% of the respondents purchased books and 3% of the respondents purchased others products. 42.7% of the respondents prefer Amazon, 31.3% of the respondents prefer Flipkart, 10% of the respondents prefer Snapdeal 6% of the respondents prefer 8% of the respondents prefer Myntra.com eBay.com and 8% of the respondents prefer Myntra.com for their purchases.

Factor Analysis:

In order to determine which factors influencing more on the behavior, Factor Analysis on 13 factors was performed (Table - 3). Principal Component Analysis with a Varimax Rotation and Eigen value equal to or more than 1 (Kinnear and Taylor, 1987) were used for the present study. In order to get clear factorial design, 2 variables with factor loadings of less than 0.50 were dropped and loadings equal to or above 0.50 were retained. The dropped variables were: can easily track the goods/service and anywhere and anytime shopping, as they have low impact. In the factor analysis, the remaining 11 variables are taken to analyze. The suitability of factor analysis was validated with the help of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy was 0.716 and Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant ($\chi^2 - 814.477, p < 0.000$).

Table: 3 Factors influencing the customers towards online shopping
 (Factor Analysis Results)

Rotated Component Matrix^a					
Component					
Variables		Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4
X2	Online shopping saving time and money	0.886			
X5	Follow as the new trend	0.855			
X6	Shopping at leisure time	0.837			
X4	Offers and seasonal discount	0.779			
X7	Easy to compare features and price	0.628			
X1	Wide range of products		0.937		
X3	Convenient Payment		0.836		
X9	Defective products are replaced properly			0.887	
X11	After sales services are satisfactory			0.835	
X8	Free home delivery				0.883
X13	Grantee and warrantee				0.712
Eigen values		3.793	2.999	1.606	1.226
Percentage of total variance		31.612	24.994	13.380	10.214
Cumulative percentage of variance		31.612	56.606	69.986	80.200
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.					

KMO and Bartlett's Test	
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	0.716

Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	814.477
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From the item's highest loading with each factor, it is understood that the first influencing factor is highly characterized by Online shopping saving time and money (0.886), Follow as the new trend (0.855), Shopping at leisure time (0.837), Offers and seasonal discount (0.779), Easy to compare features and price (0.628); second factor by Wide range of products (0.937) and Convenient Payment (0.836); third factor by Defective products are replaced properly (0.887) and After sales services are satisfactory (0.835); and fourth factor by Free home delivery (0.883) and Grantee and warrantee (0.712).

Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between Age and amount spent for online shopping.

Table 4: Chi-square test between Age and amount spent for online shopping

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	45.330	9	.000

The chi –square test is applied for further discussion. The computed chi –square value is (45.330) which is greater than its tabulate value at 5 per cent level of significance. Hence, there is a significance difference between respondents of age and amount of spent to purchasing their products through the online.

Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between monthly income and category of product purchased.

Table: 5 Chi-square test between monthly income and category of product purchased

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	40.945	15	.000

The chi –square test is applied for further discussion. The computed chi –square value is (40.945) which is greater than its tabulate value at 5 per cent level of significance. So, we concluded that there is a close relationship between monthly income and category of product purchased in online shopping.

Table 6: Level of Customer Satisfaction towards Online Shopping

Attributes	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied
Payment Security	42	106	0	0	2
	28 %	70.7 %	0		1.3 %
Price of product	46	61	43	0	0
	30.7 %	40.7 %	28.7 %		
On Time Delivery	16	74	44	14	2
	10.7 %	49.3 %	29.3 %	9.3 %	1.3 %
Product Comparison	23	64	61	2	0
	15.3 %	42.7 %	40.7 %	1.3 %	
Quality Product	6	81	51	12	0
	4 %	54 %	34 %	8 %	
Easy Return Policy	8	101	30	9	2
	5.3 %	67.3 %	20 %	6 %	1.3 %
Customer Care	0	126	22	2	0
		84 %	14.7 %	1.3 %	

The above table shows that, 70.7% of the respondents are Satisfied with Payment Security, 28% of the respondents are Highly satisfied, 1.3% of the respondents are Highly dissatisfied with regard to Payment Security, 40.7% of the respondents are satisfied in price of the product, 30.7% of the respondents are Highly Satisfied and 28.7% of the respondents are Neutral, 49.3% of the respondents are satisfied with on time delivery of the product, 29.37% of the respondents are Neutral, 10.7% of the respondents are Highly Satisfied, 9.3% of the respondents are dissatisfied and 1.3% of the respondents are highly dissatisfied. 42.7% of the respondents are satisfied in comparison of the product, 40.7% of the respondents are Neutral, 15.3% of the respondents are Highly Satisfied and 1.3% of the respondents are dissatisfied in comparison of the product. 54% of the respondents are satisfied with quality of the product, 34% of the respondents are Neutral, 5.3% of the respondents are Highly Satisfied and 9% of the respondents are dissatisfied with quality of the product. 67.3% of the respondents are satisfied with Easy Return Policy of the product, 20% of the respondents are Neutral, 6% of the respondents are dissatisfied, 5.3% of the respondents are Highly Satisfied and 1.3% of the respondents are highly dissatisfied. 84% of the respondents are satisfied with customer care services, 14.7% of the respondents are Neutral and 1.3% of the respondents are highly dissatisfied with customer care services.

Suggestions:

Online shopping is the new approach in shopping products. Mostly the online customers are in the age group of 15- 35; others not having much awareness about online shopping. The online traders should take necessary steps to create awareness among the public. The online trader has to take maximum effort to offer the wide range of products with affordable price because the price of the product plays a vital role in buying

decision. To reach the all category of consumer the online trader should use different methods of advertisement strategy. Almost all the customers prefer the cash on delivery mode to make payment for their shopping but some of the products are not available in cash on delivery option. To improve the effectiveness of online shopping this issue must be addressed.

Conclusions:

The present technological development with respect to the internet has given platform to a new marketing system. This study brought to the fact that most of the online customers are educated people and students who have a positive perception towards online shopping, in risk perception particularly concerns about online security, is preventing many people from online shopping. Ensuring adequate safety measures in delivery of products are a challenging task in front of online sellers to maximize their sales. Online traders have to resolve these problems and also need to introduce wide range of products with additional discounts. This will create more demand from customers. On the basis of analysis the present study concludes that online customers are satisfied. This research explicitly indicates that online marketer should give more importance on price and after sale service. In this competition era the entire online traders should have to concentrate on the customer's satisfaction to retain the existing customers and have to offer new scheme day by day to attract the new customers.

Scope for the Future Research:

As the present study is confined to factors influencing online buying behavior of the rural consumer, only the views of the rural consumers are given importance in this study. A study of the similar nature can be extended by covering urban consumers in the sample, and using the same methodology adopted in the present study.

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